

PREreview Clubs onboarding document

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What is a PREreview Club?

[PREreview Clubs](#) are collaborative preprint reviewing groups that form around a shared affiliation, affinity, interest, location, or any other common cause. Club members work together to offer timely, constructive peer feedback to preprint authors.

These clubs take the place of the older “Communities” on our website. We’ve overhauled those groups into our new PREreview Clubs with community feedback from design sprints, user research interviews, and collaboration with partners like [ASAPbio](#) and the [Howard Hughes Medical Institute](#) (HHMI).

How do I start a PREreview Club?

Anyone who wants to form a collaborative preprint reviewing group can ask to start a Club. While we hope to automate the process more in 2024, right now, the PREreview Team will set up the Club on your behalf. That means that you should [complete this form](#) with the required information if you’d like to start a PREreview Club. We’ll get back in touch with you to describe the rest of the process, answer your questions, and make sure PREreview Clubs are a good fit for what you want to achieve.

If everything seems right, we’ll get your Clubs page set up and go through our workflow with you to make sure that your Club and all its participating authors are credited on the reviews you author together.

We will need the following information from you:

- The name of your PREreview Club.
- A short blurb describing the purpose of your PREreview Club and how frequently you plan to author reviews together.
- Your name (as PREreview Club Lead).

- The names of PREreview Club members who would like to be listed publicly as other club leads.
- The research areas that interest your PREreview Club the most.
- Optional: A URL for a “Join this club!” button if you would like us to include that button and make your club open to anyone.

You might start a PREreview Club based on affinity, geography, or language. You might also start a club for your class, lab, institution, or organization. You might even start a club for your friends who love collaborative preprint review!

If you're interested, remember to [complete this form](#) to learn more!

What does a PREreview Club webpage look like?

It looks a bit like this, though we may update the format of this page from time to time.

The screenshot shows the club page for 'ASAPbio Neurobiology Crowd'. At the top left is the PREREVIEW logo. To the right are navigation links: Reviews, Trainings, Preprint journal clubs, Communities, and Partners. The main heading is 'ASAPbio Neurobiology Crowd'. Below it is a description: 'The ASAPbio Neurobiology Crowd reviews preprints that focus on neurodevelopment and neurodegeneration.' Under 'Club leads', it lists 'Bhargy Sharma, Anna Oliveras, and Ryan John Cubero' with ORCID icons. A red 'Join the club' button is present. The 'PREreviews' section lists two reviews: one by Anna Oliveras, Mayank Chugh, Bhargy Sharma, and Femi Arogundade on August 2, 2023, and another by Ryan John Cubero and 1 other author on July 31, 2023. Both reviews are linked to bioRxiv.

This is a screenshot of the ASAPbio Neurobiology Crowd club page on PREreview.org. It lists the name of the club, a description of the club, the names of its club leads, a join the club button, and a list of PREreviews authored by the club.

What do I have to do as a PREreview Club Lead?

- PREreview Clubs leads:
 - Manage their clubs membership and review activities.
 - This means that you can recruit and manage membership however you'd like.
 - You can also schedule collaborative reviews, compose them on any platform you'd like, and publish them on PREreview whenever you are ready.
 - If you could use help with outreach or organizing your club, let us know at community@prereview.org.
 - If you need technical help, let us know at help@prereview.org.
 - Ask each club member to create an ORCIDiD and PREreview account.
 - This will give them a public profile and a more confidential pseudonymous profile that they can choose from when it's time to credit them for a review.
 - Publish reviews when they are ready on PREreview.org.
 - Responsibly and consentfully manage useful club members' data that's necessary to give them credit for their work, such as email addresses and ORCIDiDs.

What happens when someone publishes a review for my PREreview Club?

- Once you publish a PREreview:
 - The PREreview is published on Zenodo and PREreview.org and gets its own DOI.
 - Contributing authors get emails from us asking how they would like us to credit them. For example, they can let us know if they'd like us to list their public profile or pseudonymous profile on PREreview.org.
 - We at PREreview update the backend of the PREreview's Zenodo record to connect it to your club.
 - Your club's name and your club members' names (either public or pseudonymous) are listed on the review.
 - Club members who have opted into our ORCID integration will have the review listed on their ORCID profiles as peer review activity
 - The review itself is listed on your club's page on PREreview.org.

We will also create a list on [Society](https://www.society.org/) to curate your club's PREreview activity so that it is discoverable by that community, as well. ([Example club list.](#)) You can provide us with a logo for your list if you'd like.

What if I need help?

To start the PREreview Clubs process, please [complete this form](#).

To get technical help with a PREreview Club's webpage or reviews, please email help@prereview.org. You can also reach us on the #help channel on the PREreview community Slack.

To get help with strategies for outreach and events for your PREreview Club, please email community@prereview.org

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